

GRAPE-based slab-selective universal parallel
transmit excitation pulses for whole-brain MRSI
at 7 Tesla

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Impact

This work shows the feasibility of GRAPE-based frequency-selective universal parallel transmit excitation pulses (GRAPE-UPs) for whole-brain MRSI. These reduce spatial flip angle variations, and the resulting SNR loss, which is one of the main difficulties in whole-brain MRSI at ultra-high field.

Synopsis

Motivation

Whole-brain MRSI at ultra-high field is hampered by the excitation field inhomogeneity which causes flip angle variations and, consequently, reduced SNR, especially in the cerebellum.

Goals

To improve the flip angle homogeneity and, consequently, increase the SNR of whole-brain ultra-high field MRSI by utilizing universal pTx-pulses.

Approach

Frequency-selective universal pulses (UPs) were designed for homogeneous excitation with the GRAPE approach and implemented in a pulse-acquire-based MRSI sequence with concentric-ring readout at 7T. The spectral SNR was estimated with LCMoel and compared to CP excitation.

Result

GRAPE-UP excitation achieves a mean SNR increase of 23% in the cerebellum. A slight SNR increase was also observed over the whole brain.

Abstract

Background and Focus

The measurement of whole-brain metabolic concentration maps has become feasible by using fast readouts and ultra-high field[1]. The nominal flip angle of the excitation pulse in an MRSI measurement is usually set to the Ernst angle for optimal SNR. However, the inhomogeneous excitation field causes strong spatial flip angle variability, resulting in reduced SNR. Universal[2] parallel-transmit (ptx)-pulses (UPs) might offer improved performance. The cerebellum, which is especially effected by this inhomogeneity, will be of special focus.

Methods

In a preceding database study, 20 subjects were measured in a 7T-Plus scanner (Siemens Healthineers), using a 32-channel receive, 8-channel transmit coil (Nova Medical). For each subject, B_0 maps and individual-channel B_1 maps were acquired[3]. In order to design frequency-selective GRAPE-UP pulses, a random off-center frequency was added to each voxel of the B_0 maps. This ensured a pseudo-continuous frequency distribution. Then, the target flip angle is defined as a function of the added off-center frequency. Afterwards, the RF and gradient waveforms were simultaneously optimized for the whole database, utilizing the GRAPE[4] algorithm. Slab-selective excitation was either performed with a 600us long filtered sinc-shaped CP excitation pulse with 6kHz bandwidth or with a duration-matched, slab-selective GRAPE-UP. The GRAPE optimization was given a box function with 7kHz bandwidth and 42° flip angle as target and a target excitation phase, linear to the off-center frequency. The pulse was initialized with a sinc-shaped CP pulse.

Figure fig. 1 shows the optimized RF (only 3 channels) and gradient waveforms of the GRAPE-UP excitation. The top plots in Figure fig. 2 show a coronal slice of simulated flip angle maps in of one subject from the database study for CP excitation and GRAPE-UP, showing improved homogeneity. The bottom plot shows as a function of off-center frequency: the mean flip angle in this subject (black), the root-mean-square error to the target of 42° (red) and the flip angle of an example voxel (blue).

The GRAPE-UPs were implemented in a pulse-acquire-based MRSI sequence with concentric-ring readout[5]. Two MRSI acquisitions, with GRAPE-UP and CP excitation respectively, have been performed on one healthy volunteer who was not in the database. Coil combination was performed with iMUSICAL[6], using scaled versions of the respective excitation pulse. WET[7] water suppression was performed. All sequence parameters were kept constant (TE/TR=1.3ms/600ms, 5mm isotropic resolution, matrix size: 44x44x39, 155mm slab thickness, 42° flip angle). Additionally, an MPRAGE[8] was acquired.

Spectral quantification was performed voxel-wise using LCModel[9] with CP-optimized basis functions. The spectral SNR was estimated by the LCModel

output. From the MPRAGE, whole brain and cerebellum masks were calculated using ANTs[10].

Results

Figure fig. 3 shows histograms of the spectral SNR in the cerebellum and in the whole brain. Qualitatively the distributions look similar for both excitations. In the whole brain, the mean SNR is 4,5% higher if GRAPE excitation is used (12.6 vs 12.0). In the cerebellum however, the mean SNR is 23.4% higher if GRAPE excitation is used (7.60 vs. 6,16). Note, that the NAA concentration is lower in the cerebellum, which causes the LCModel SNR estimate to be lower, compared to the whole brain. Figure fig. 4 shows a coronal slice of spectral SNR map of both measurements. The increase of SNR in the cerebellum is obvious. Note, that the increase in SNR is despite not using basis functions, simulated for GRAPE excitation.

Figure fig. 5 shows a coronal slice of the Glx/tNAA and tCho/tCr metabolic ratio maps obtained with CP and GRAPE-UP excitation, next the corresponding slices of the MPRAGE and its segmentation. Gray matter to white matter contrast is visible in the metabolic maps. In most parts of the brain, similar data quality is achieved with both excitations. In the lower parts of the cerebellum, however, artificially high Glx/tNAA values are observed with CP excitation. This reduction of data quality is less obvious in the tCho/tCr ratio maps.

Conclusion

The feasibility of GRAPE-UPs for slab-selective excitation for MRSI has been shown in one subject. In the whole brain, a slight increase of mean spectral SNR could be observed. The SNR gain of 23% in the cerebellum improved the quality of metabolic ratio maps in this brain region. Thus, GRAPE-UP excitation might be well-suited for whole-brain MRSI applications at 7T. In the future, the preliminary results need to be confirmed through more data from healthy subjects and patients. Additionally, we will extend the approach to the WET module of the MRSI sequence.

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Images

Figure 1: RF amplitude (top) and phase (middle) of three different channels. Some channels (channels 1 and 3) resemble the initial sinc initialization, while others (channel 5) have a different shape. The bottom plot shows the gradient waveform.

Figure 2: Top: coronal slices of the simulated flip angle map using CP excitation (left) and GRAPE-UP (right) The central brightening effect which is prominent in the CP map is reduced by GRAPE excitation. Bottom: mean flip angle (black), root-mean-square error (red) and flip angle in an example voxel (red circle) as a function of frequency. In this subject, the flip angle is slightly reduced. Note that the simulation were performed without slab-selection gradient to emphasize the effect of field inhomogeneities.

Figure 3: Histograms of the spectral SNR in the whole brain (top) and in the cerebellum (bottom) for CP excitation (red) and GRAPE-UP (orange) excitation. In the whole brain, the histograms are relatively similar. However, GRAPE excitation leads to slightly higher mean SNR. In the cerebellum, the CP histograms appears to be more compressed and on average, lower values are achieved.

Figure 4: Coronal slice of the SNR maps, measured with CP excitation (left) and GRAPE-UP (middle). On the right, the corresponding slice of the MPRAGE is depicted. While in the cerebrum, no major difference between both SNR maps is visible, the SNR in the cerebellum is clearly increased by GRAPE-UP excitation

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Figure 5: Coronal slice of the Glx/tNAA (top) and tCho/Cr (bottom) metabolic ratio maps measured with CP excitation (left) and GRAPE-UP (middle). On the right the MPRAGE and the segmentation results are shown. Gray matter to white matter contrast is clearly visible in the four metabolic ratio maps and in most parts of the brain, the image quality appears to be similar. In the lower parts of the cerebellum, the image quality reduced for CP excitation.

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